

Sample 12a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0021
	{Si}	37.6
	{Al, Si}	8.9
	{Ca}	7.9
	{Fe}	7.8
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.9
	{Cl}	3.7
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.9
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.6
	{Al, Si, K}	2.3
	{S, Ca}	2.1
	{Cl}	2.0
	{Si, Ca HIP}	1.8
	{Si, Fe}	1.4
	{Mg, Ca}	1.4
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.2
	{Si, Cl}	1.1
	{Na, Si}	0.9
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.9
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.8
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.7
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Zn-LA1}	0.5
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Si, Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.5
Pellet	2.4
Ore preparation undifferentiated	4.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	1.9
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.1
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.2
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.1
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.5
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	5.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.7
Carbon rich - other	4.8
Cement or BOF converter	5.0
Cement	2.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.3
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.5
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.3
Salt or salt layer	0.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	44.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	18.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.1
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.1

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	7.9
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	3.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	2.1
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.5
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	5.0
Site - carbon-rich other	0.7
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	5.0
Urban	3.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.1
Natural mineral background	44.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	18.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 12b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0017
	{Si}	48.1
	{Al, Si}	7.6
	{Ca}	5.1
	{Fe}	4.6
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.6
	{S, Ca}	2.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.6
	{Cl}	2.4
	{Al, Si, K}	2.0
	{Cl}	1.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.5
	{Na, Si}	1.3
	{Mg, Si}	1.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	1.1
	{Si, Ca HIP}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	1.1
	{Si, Fe}	1.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.9
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Si, K}	0.7
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.6
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.5
	{Zn-LA1}	0.4
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Al}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Si, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.6
Pellet	2.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.2
BOF converter slag	0.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.1
Desulphur slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.6
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.1
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.7
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	5.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.3
Carbon rich - other	5.2
Cement or BOF converter	2.1
Cement	2.5
Gypsum or anhydrite	1.1
Ti-rich paint	0.4
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.6
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	53.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	15.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.9
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	1.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.3
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	4.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.2
Site - slag	1.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	2.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.7
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	5.0
Site - carbon-rich other	0.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	5.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	2.1
Urban	4.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	53.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	15.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.9
Unknown	1.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 12c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0013
	{Si}	46.6
	{Ca}	10.2
	{Al, Si}	6.7
	{Fe}	4.6
	{Cl}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.4
	{Na, Al, Si}	3.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.0
	{Al, Si, K}	2.1
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.8
	{Cl}	1.5
	{S, Ca}	1.4
	{Na, Si}	1.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.1
	{Si, Fe}	1.0
	{Si, Cl}	0.8
	{Mg, Si}	0.6
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.4
	{Zn-LA1}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Cl, Ca}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	1.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	3.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.2
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Olivine flux	0.6
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	5.6
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	6.1
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.2
Carbon rich - other	4.3
Cement or BOF converter	3.2
Cement	3.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.4
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.9
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.2
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	51.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	12.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.2
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.3

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	3.8
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	3.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	5.6
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.1
Site - carbon-rich other	1.2
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	4.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	3.2
Urban	4.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	51.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	12.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels